

A Web-based software for randomization tests of cluster analysis of invertebrate biodiversity in a rice ecosystem

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As an important analytical tool, cluster analysis is widely used in ecological research—e.g., community classification, biological evolution analyses, and biogeographic comparisons (Krebs 1989). Dozens of algorithms for cluster analysis have been developed for common use or special purposes (Zhang and Fang 1982). Most of them, however, do not use appropriate statistical tests in the computation procedures. Thus, we are not able to evaluate statistically the confidence of the classifications in the cluster analysis. Classical statistics can be used to answer the above question when statistical assumptions on data have been met. For example, are the individuals randomly sampled from the population of interest? Do clustered individuals come from different populations or groups that share equal population standard deviations or means? Do the values coincide with a normal distribution or with other known distributions (Manly 1997)? Unfortunately, these assumptions are usually not met in most ecological studies. The randomization method, always featuring fewer statistical restrictions, provides an effective method for testing the statistical significance of ecological data and has been used in ecologi-

cal studies (Manly 1997, Zhang and Schoenly 2001). In this paper, the algorithm of cluster analysis with a randomization test procedure was developed and implemented as the Web-based software StatTestCluster. It contains four procedures: weighting and standardization of the data, calculation of distance measures, hierarchical clustering, and a randomization statistical test.

Assume that the data (abundance, occurrence, etc.) for the i th sample and j th taxon are a_{ij} , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$; $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Weights can be set for each taxon to denote its relative importance (e.g., in integrated pest management, the more economically important the pest is, the larger weight should be set for it). The weight of the i th taxon is w_i , and it should meet $w_i > 0$, $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1$. Thus, the input data will be $a_{ij} = w_i a_{ij}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$; $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. The input data can be standardized by mapping them to the range $[-1, +1]$ or $[0, 1]$ (Zhang and Fang 1982). Data can only be standardized if a quantitative distance measure is chosen.

Fourteen distance (or similarity) measures, including measures for continuous values, Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, Chebyshev distance, correlation coefficient, and angular

cosine; measures for multiple discrete values, linkage coefficient, colinkage coefficients 1–3; and measures for Boolean values, point correlation coefficient, quadratic correlation coefficient, angular cosines 1–2, and Jacarrd coefficient, are available for selection by users (Zhang and Fang 1982, Qi and Zhang 2003).

At first, each sample makes a class. Five algorithms define between-class dissimilarities: nearest neighbor, farthest neighbor, class average, centroid clustering, and sum of square deviations (Zhang and Fang 1982, Krebs 1989). Between-class distance for these algorithms is respectively defined as the shortest distance between samples, the longest distance between samples, the square root of the average squared distance between two samples in two classes, the distance between weighted centers (each center is the mean of samples in the same class), and the sum of squared deviations. For this last distance measure, assume that the sum of squared deviations for class P and Q is p and q , respectively. Combine P and Q into a new class R, and, if the sum of squared deviations for class R is r , then the distance between P and Q is $r - p - q$. Select classes P and Q for which this distance is smallest and combine them into a

new class, R. For each cycle of clustering, the number of classes will decrease until all samples are combined into the same class.

The randomization test procedure is described by the following steps: assume that a class, C, is divided into two classes, A and B, which contain n_A and n_B samples of class C, respectively. The n_A+n_B samples of class C randomly reallocate into two classes with n_A and n_B samples. Calculate the expected distance between the two pseudoclasses and compare whether it is greater than the distance between the classes A and B. Repeat the simulation many times, calculate the number of times the expected distance is greater than the distance between classes A and B, and take the percentage as the p value. The p value is used to make a statistical test. The threshold p value for the test can be defined as 0.1, 0.05, etc. If the calculated p value is less than the p threshold, then class C can be divided into classes A and B with statistical significance; if the calculated p value is greater than the p threshold, then class C cannot be reliably divided into classes A and B.

The software StatTest Cluster provides this statistical test of classifications so that users can decide whether the current classification should be trusted or not. The software was programmed in Java Applet and HTML to enable interactive operations on the Internet, to allow easy access to users worldwide, and for use in teaching programs and online research. Before using the software, users must have

the Web browser Java enabled.

Algorithm details can be found by clicking on "Hint" on the Applet window. A window will pop up to show algorithm details, data file format, and references. Users must enter the number of samples, the number of taxa (indices), the number of randomizations (e.g., 100 or 1,000), the threshold of statistical significance level (i.e., 0.1 means a 90% degree of confidence), and specify the cluster data file by clicking on "Open Clustering File." A dialog box will pop up waiting for a data file to be chosen. Finally, the software can be run and the results window and cluster tree window will appear after the computation is finished. The cluster data file is a plain text file with an extension ".txt". The current classification in the output file can be considered statistically significant if $P \leq$ the threshold significance level. By clicking on "Save," users can save cluster results as a plain text file. The cluster tree can be rotated by clicking on "Rotate" on the cluster tree window. If an error occurs (e.g., the user forgot to enter parameter values), a warning window will appear.

In this study, 10 samples of rice invertebrates were collected from Guangdong rice fields and these samples were classified using StatTest Cluster (Euclidean distance, class average, nontaxa weighting, standard deviation standardization, 100 randomizations, a threshold significance level of 0.1). Results

are indicated as follows. The cluster tree (omitted) can be used, but we should focus on the significance of the statistical test on each classification in the following:

```
Clustering Distance=0.0
(1) (6) (2) (4) (7) (5) (9) (10) (3) (8)

p=0.0*
Clustering Distance=0.3094
(1) (6) (2) (4) (7) (5) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.0*
Clustering Distance=0.3235
(1) (6) (2 4) (7) (5) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.0*
Clustering Distance=0.8041
(1 6) (2 4) (7) (5) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.0*
Clustering Distance=0.9186
(1 6) (2 4 7) (5) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.88
Clustering Distance=1.0311
(1 2 4 6 7) (5) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.83
Clustering Distance=1.1957
(1 2 4 5 6 7) (9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.05*
Clustering Distance=1.3828
(1 2 4 5 6 7 9 10) (3) (8)

p=0.67
Clustering Distance=1.5261
(1 2 3 4 5 6 7 9 10) (8)

p=0.92
Clustering Distance=1.8961
(1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10)
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In this cluster analysis, as indicated by the P values (labeled by the symbol "*"), the following classifications are considered to be statistically significant (1 2 4 5 6 7 9 10) $\rightarrow$ (1 2 4 5 6 7) + (9 10), (2 4 7) $\rightarrow$ (2 4) + (7), (1 6) $\rightarrow$ (1) + (6), (2 4) $\rightarrow$ (2) + (4), (9 10) $\rightarrow$ (9) + (10). In classical cluster analysis, P values were not given so we could not determine whether the classification was reliable or not.

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Detection of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* by NCM-ELISA in naturally infected rice plants

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Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) is an economically important bacterial disease (Mew 1987). Effective control techniques need to be developed to improve crop production in the country. The spread of BB occurs through plant debris, weeds, water, and seeds. Hence, early detection and identification of the pathogen are crucial in an integrated disease management program. This can be done through seed health testing and plant quarantine.

Conventional techniques are currently being used in disease diagnoses, particularly in developing countries. These techniques are still applicable, though they are less effective and are time-consuming. Serological and molecular approaches have shown effectiveness because they are accurate and fast. However, adoption of the latter techniques very much de-

pends on the availability of equipment and affordability of chemicals.

Serological assays such as the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and its variant need to be developed and made readily applicable for field users. Previous trials indicate that ELISA was effective in detecting plant pathogens such as *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith et al 1995). This study aims to develop a polyclonal antibody (pAb) against *Xoo* for practical use in BB detection.

Naturally infected rice plants were collected and isolated from rice fields in West Java and Central Java during the 2003 planting season. A laboratory experiment was conducted at ICABGR-Bogor and IRIR-Sukamandi. Each sample was stored in a freezer until required. Infected leaves were grown on Wakimoto agar medium for 3 d, adjusted to a concentration

of 10^9 cfu ml⁻¹. Bacterial whole cells of *Xoo* isolates, fixed with 2% glutaraldehyde, formalin, or untreated antigen, were used to immunize a white New Zealand rabbit. Two intramuscular injections were made on the rabbit with cells of *Xoo* in a 5-mL saline solution mixed with either the same volume of complete or incomplete Freund's adjuvant. Crude antiserum was pooled and partially purified using ammonium sulfate precipitation following serial dialysis processes using phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). pAb was measured by a spectrophotometer using an absorbance value of 280 and 260, assuming that optical density $(OD)_{280/260} = 1.4$ is equivalent to protein of 1 mg mL⁻¹.

Collected samples of *Xoo* were further tested by nitrocellulose membrane (NCM)-ELISA following the protocol of Fuentes (1993). One hundred μ L of whole cells diluted